

NATI00NS

Deliverable 3.2 – Review of National engagement events, round #1

National engagement activities to support the launch of the Mission 'A Soil Deal for Europe' 100 Living Labs and Lighthouses

Data sheet

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Glossary of terms

Term	Description
AC	Associated Country
DEC	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication
EC	European Commission
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LH	(Soil health) Lighthouse
LL	(Soil health) Living Lab
MS	Member State
REA	Research Executive Agency

Keywords

Soil health, Living Labs, Lighthouses, EU Soil Mission, National Engagement Event

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Executive Summary

This deliverable reflects on the success of the national engagement events held across 43 EU Member States and Associated Countries. These events effectively contributed to raising awareness of the EU Soil Mission and its open calls, attracting more than 2400 combined participants across countries and regions.

The feedback collected during these events has been instrumental in shaping subsequent project tasks and initiatives. It has influenced the development of impactful webinars, the growth of the matchmaking platform, and upcoming online thematic events. The insights gained from participants have not only enhanced the effectiveness of these components but also contributed to fostering stronger collaborations and knowledge exchange within the soil health community.

As the project moves forward, the lessons learned from the engagement events will be central in NATIOONS' success in supporting the EU Soil Mission, furthering its mission to preserve and revitalise soil resources for the benefit of present and future generations.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Background and Objectives

The deliverable 3.2 is part of a three-month event implementation process supporting the ambitious goals of the EU Mission ‘A Soil Deal for Europe’ (hereafter, the Mission), which aims at establishing one hundred soil health Living Labs (LLs) and Lighthouses (LHs) across Europe by 2030. NATIOONS supports the Mission in its early stages by acting as an ambassador and conveying the main awareness raising messages to national and regional stakeholders. The project provides access to capacity building materials and information and fosters early matchmaking for cross-regional LL clusters addressing land uses: agriculture, nature, forestry, urban, and (post) industrial.

This deliverable is a report which represents the conclusion of the first part of a reporting process. It provides information about the results and outcomes of the first round of NATIOONS national engagement events. This document provides a comprehensive overview of the event implementation, participant feedback, and the effectiveness of the engagement strategies employed. It also highlights the challenges encountered, and recommendations for future improvements. The reporting ensures transparency, accountability, and knowledge sharing among project partners and stakeholders.

The first round of national engagement events took place in the period 1 March – 5 June 2023 within the framework of the Work Package 3 (WP3) activities.

WP3 – National Engagement Events – has been specifically designed to successfully organise and execute two rounds of national engagement events, and prepare stakeholders for the calls for proposals supporting the implementation of the LLs and LHs across Europe. WP3 is made of three tasks: (1) T3.1 Overarching event organisation and supervision; (2) T3.2 Implementation and evaluation of National engagement events; (3) T3.3 Innovation potential thematic events. Each of them covers specific phases of the projects.

The deliverable D3.2 is part of the work carried out in T3.2. It reports on the lessons learnt from the first round of events to enhance the optimisation of the entire organisation process for the second-round while addressing any potential bottleneck and flaws.

All the takeaways in this document are capitalised in the creation of capacity-building materials as part of the project’s knowledge exploitation activities in T2.3. Furthermore, they are also to be shared with the Mission Secretariat, the PREPSOIL project (GA 101070045) and the SOILL project (GA 101112782, Framework Partnership Agreement (FPA) for a Living Lab network support structure), and the Mission Implementation Platform. These insights are evaluated to increase the efforts in certain countries and regions where it could be sensible to enhance the support of NATIOONS for the second round of events to actually ensure equal opportunities for the stakeholders across Europe.

1.2 Task Participants

TRUST-IT (Trust-IT srl) leads and coordinates the activities of task 3.2 - Implementation and evaluation of National engagement events (M4 – M18), as well as organises events in Italy, Armenia and Georgia. The other partners supporting the implementation of the activities are reported in the following table, which also remarks their roles within the task.

Short name	Legal name	Role in the task
AU	AARHUS UNIVERSITET	Setting-up, holding, following-up on the National Engagement Event in Denmark. Liaising with REA and the Mission Secretariat
ENoLL	EUROPEAN NETWORK OF LIVING LABS IVZW	Setting-up, holding, following-up on the National Engagement Event in Belgium, Luxembourg and Ireland.
EIT-FOOD	EIT FOOD CLC SOUTH S.L.	Setting-up, holding, following-up on the National Engagement Event in Cyprus, Israel, Turkey.
FUNDECYT-PCTEX	FUNDACION FUNDECYT – PARQUE CIENTIFICO Y TECNOLOGICO DE EXTREMADURA	Setting-up, holding, following-up on the National Engagement Event in France, Greece, Germany, Netherland, Portugal, Spain.
COMMpla	COMMPLA SRL	ICT support to the management of the events on the project website.
BIOSENSE	BIOSENSE INSTITUTE – RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT INSTITUTE FOR INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN BIOSYSTEMS	Setting-up, holding, following-up on the National Engagement Event in Bosnia and Herzegovina, Kosovo, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Serbia.
IUNG	INSTYTUT UPRAWY NAWOZENIA I GLEBOZNAWSTWA, PANSTWOWY INSTYTUT BADAWCZY	Setting-up, holding, following-up on the National Engagement Event in Czech Republic, Poland, Slovakia.
XIA	EXPRESS INNOVATION AGENCY VMV NONPROFIT ZARTKORUEN MUKODO RESZVENYTARSASAG	Setting-up, holding, following-up on the National Engagement Event in Croatia, Hungary, Slovenia.
LAAS	VIESOJI ISTAIGA LIETUVOS ZEMES UKIO KONSULTAVIMO TARNYBA	Setting-up, holding, following-up on the National Engagement Event in Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania.
IRCEM	ASOCIATIA INSTITUTUL PENTRU CERCETARE IN ECONOMIE CIRCULARA SI MEDIU EERNEST LUPAN IRCEM	Setting-up, holding, following-up on the National Engagement Event in Moldova, Romania, Ukraine.
BMED	UNION MEDITERRANEENNE DES CONFEDERATIONS D'ENTREPRISES	Setting-up, holding, following-up on the National Engagement Event in Malta, Tunisia.
SLU	SVERIGES LANTBRUKSUNIVERSITET	Setting-up, holding, following-up on the National Engagement Event in Finland, Iceland, Norway, Sweden.

Table 1. Task Participants

1.3 Relations with other deliverables

To support the successful implementation of the national engagement events, several other deliverables play crucial roles. Deliverable 1.1 - the stakeholder analysis - provides a comprehensive list of stakeholders at European and national levels. This analysis helps identify and understand the target audience for the events, ensuring that the engagement strategies are tailored effectively. Deliverable 1.2, the content generation plan, outlines the detailed materials to be produced for WP3 and WP4 activities. While this deliverable is publicly available, it serves as a reference for D3.2 to align the event materials and outputs with the overall project objectives.

The update of the content generation plan, as captured in D1.3, may introduce modifications or additions to the initial plan. D3.2 contributes to fine-tune these updates to ensure that the event materials remain relevant and up to date, reflecting any changes or enhancements made throughout the project. D1.4, the cooperation plan, identifies opportunities for collaboration with sister projects, initiatives, and organizations. The insights provided with the data collected for this plan has informed T3.2 partners in leveraging potential partnerships during the national engagement events, further enhancing stakeholder engagement and knowledge sharing.

D3.2 aligns with the dissemination, exploitation, and communication (DEC) plan outlined in D2.1, as that strategic document ensures that the results and outcomes of the national engagement events are effectively communicated to relevant stakeholders. Additionally, any insights emerging from D3.2 will feed the updated version of DEC plan, which will be reflected in D2.2 – the update of dissemination, exploitation and communication plan.

The overarching event plan with guidelines for event organisers, as described in D3.1, provides a framework for the smooth completion of the national events. T3.2 and D3.2 build upon this plan, ensuring consistency and adherence to the established guidelines during the implementation and evaluation of the events. D3.3, the review of events, will complement the performance review conducted in D3.2. This deliverable will offer additional insights and perspectives on the national engagement events, providing a comprehensive evaluation of their outcomes, successes, challenges, and recommendations for future improvements.

The coaching and capacity-building report (D4.1), evaluates the effectiveness of the capacity-building efforts in enhancing stakeholder engagement during the first round of national engagement events. The capacity-building materials produced in T4.2 expand the information that are conveyed in the National engagement events, especially on how to support the Living Labs before and within the application process to the open calls, as well as on expanding their knowledge on soil health.

These materials are developed as e-factsheets and are publicly available on the project's website, on the NATIOONS' Zenodo Community¹ and posted on PREPSOIL's one-stop shop. D3.2 references

¹ Community of NATIOONS in Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/communities/natio0ons/>.

D4.1 to assess the impact of capacity-building activities and incorporate any lessons learned into future event planning.

Lastly, D4.4 (M11 – September 2023), the helpdesk performance report for the first round of events, will provide performance metrics for the helpdesk operation during the project. D3.2 provide additional information to evaluate the support provided to participants during the national engagement events and identify areas for improvement in providing assistance and guidance. D3.2 leverages insights, analyses, plans, and reports from these deliverables, and feeds some of them with a comprehensive overview of the event implementation, participant feedback, effectiveness of engagement strategies, challenges encountered, and recommendations for future improvements.

2 Implementation of the National Engagement Events

2.1 Overview of T3.2 Activities

Task 3.2, titled "Implementation and evaluation of National engagement events," runs as part of the NATIOONS project from Month 4 to Month 18. The lead partner for this task is Trust-IT, and it involves the participation of several other project partners (see 1.2). The objective of this task is to organise and evaluate the national engagement events as outlined in Task 3.1. At this stage, and for the purpose of this deliverable, during the execution of the first round of national engagement events, each partner played a vital role in organising and hosting the events. They leveraged their local expertise and networks to ensure the events were tailored to the specific needs and characteristics of their respective countries or regions. This localised approach allowed for targeted engagement with stakeholders and maximised the impact of the events.

To measure the performance of the first round of national engagement events, various key performance indicators (KPIs) were defined. These KPIs included metrics such as event attendance, participant feedback, level of stakeholder satisfaction, and the themes that generated more interest as a result of the events. The task partners closely monitored these KPIs and contributed to compile event statistics, which captured the outcomes, successes, challenges, and recommendations for each event. The insights resulting from the national engagement events were used to develop e-learning materials, described in T4.2 – Preparing e-learning materials. This content aims to support stakeholders in effectively developing and implementing Living Lab proposals. The materials include useful information and practical tips that are derived from the experiences and knowledge that the events contributed to consolidating. The materials have been shared within the project consortium and made available for wider dissemination to benefit stakeholders beyond the project on the open repository Zenodo, whose link is also available on the NATIOONS website.

2.1.1 Evaluation by the NATIOONS Executive Board and Relation with the Mission Secretariat

The evaluation of the first round of national engagement events entailed a collaborative and seamless dialogue between the NATIOONS WP leads and the Mission Secretariat for getting the optimal

feedback from the evaluation of the events. The evaluation process involved a thorough analysis of the event reports, participant feedback, and the achievement of predefined KPIs. The evaluation aimed to assess the overall success of the events, identify areas for improvement, and inform decision-making for the second round. The evaluation also involved assessing the support needs of different countries and regions. It considered factors such as the level of stakeholder engagement, regional disparities, and the readiness of stakeholders to participate in Living Lab initiatives. This analysis helped identify countries or regions where additional support and resources were required to foster their participation and ensure a balanced representation across Europe.

2.1.2 Redistributing Resources

Based on the evaluation outcomes, the consortium will consider a reallocation of resources in support of countries or regions that demonstrated higher support requirements. The goal is to optimise the use of available resources and maximise the impact of the events by targeting support where it is most needed. This approach aims to create equal opportunities and ensure broad and diverse stakeholder engagement across Europe.

2.1.3 Conclusion of the overview

Task 3.2 successfully implemented and evaluated the national engagement events, showcasing the collaborative efforts of the project partners. The localised approach to event execution, performance measurement, and capacity building enabled effective stakeholder engagement and knowledge sharing. The evaluation process, in conjunction with the analysis of support needs, facilitates the discussion of redistribution of resources to ensure equitable opportunities for participation across Europe. The outcomes of Task 3.2 contribute to the achievement of project objectives and foster a strong foundation for the development of Living Lab proposals and future knowledge exploitation activities.

2.2 Event Structure and Timeline

The overall structure of the national events was outlined in D3.1 “Overarching event plan with guidelines for event organisers”, identifying a set of core sessions to be featured in all events and foreseeing a degree of flexibility for additional sessions. Events were scheduled to be about 2-4 hours, to cover the most relevant aspects of the programme.

Core sessions

1. A session dedicated to **present the EU Mission “A Soil Deal for Europe**, to provide a bird’s-eye view of the Mission, generally adapted to the national environment.
2. A session to explain soil health **Living Laboratories and Lighthouses**, highlighting their differences and providing real-life examples. It will also cover the Open Call's application form to assist interested attendees in their submissions.
3. **One or more engagement session(s)**; a space to encourage participant interaction via Q&As, breakouts, also with the support of digital tools such as sli.do and Mural.

In addition, organisers and co-organisers could also include other related activities, such as panel discussions, matchmaking sessions, group activities (e.g., games, visits to sites and others).

The national engagement events are listed in the table below.

We have experienced an unforeseen issue with the event in Austria, which has not been carried out in the first round.

Austria: Official Soil Mission events took place before the start of NATIOONS in September-October 2022, while a physical meeting was organised on 9 May with a focus on soil related topics and specifically about EJP Soil projects, in which the NCP is going to talk about the Soil Mission and Living Labs². As this was an external event, the NCP could not help in getting NATIOONS into the programme. Unfortunately, this clashed with our intentions of organising an event in Austria. This will surely be addressed in the second round.

Date	Country	Link	Participants	Notes
01.03.2023	Spain	https://natio0ns.eu/events/jornada-nacional-mision-suelo-horizonte-europa	99	
01.03.2023	United Kingdom	https://natio0ns.eu/events/horizon-europe-mission-soil-deal-europe-community-building-event-uk		Online only. Participated in UK KTN webinar.
10.03.2023	Romania	https://natio0ns.eu/events/misiunea-soluri-sustenabile-uniunii-europene-romania	94	
10.03.2023	Italy	https://natio0ns.eu/events/evento-nazionale-missione-suolo-unione-europea-living-labs-lighthouses	95	
13.03.2023	Moldova	https://natio0ns.eu/events/misiunea-soluri-sustenabile-uniunii-europene-republica-moldova	64	
15.03.2023	Denmark	https://natio0ns.eu/events/dansk-engagement-event-fokus-pa-jordens-sundhed	67	In-person only
21.03.2023	Israel	https://natio0ns.eu/events/eu-soil-mission-event-israel-funding-opportunities-living-lab-creation	61	
21.03.2023	Ukraine	https://natio0ns.eu/events/nacionalni-zakhod-schodo-zaluchennya-ukraine	17	Online only
23.03.2023	Turkey	https://natio0ns.eu/events/ab-toprak-misyonu-fiansman-firsatlari-ve-turkiyede-rejeneratif-tarim-uygulamalari	67	

² <https://www.bodeninfo.net/termine-und-initiativen/bodenforum-oesterreich/>

Date	Country	Link	Participants	Notes
23.03.2023	Hungary	https://nati00ns.eu/events/horizont-europa-talaj-misszoiat-tamogato-nemzeti-informacios-nap	82	
23.03.2023	Belgium	https://nati00ns.eu/events/national-engagement-event-eu-soil-mission-belgium	74	
23.03.2023	Sweden	https://nati00ns.eu/events/living-labs-med-fokus-pa-jordhalsa-national-engagement-event-sverige	41	
24.03.2023	Ireland	https://nati00ns.eu/events/national-engagement-event-eu-soil-mission-ireland	32	
24.03.2023	Bulgaria	https://nati00ns.eu/events/nacionalno-sbitie-za-predstavvane-na-misiya-pakt-za-pochvite-v-evropa	67	
29.03.2023	France	https://nati00ns.eu/events/journee-information-living-labs-mission-sols-horizon-europe	84	Collaboration with MESR, INRAE, ACTA, RNEST
29.03.2023	Serbia	https://nati00ns.eu/events/nati00ns-zdravo-zemljiste-zdrav-zivot-predstavljanje-prilika-fondova-evropske-unije-za	52	
04.04.2023	Serbia	https://nati00ns.eu/events/predstavljanje-prilika-fondova-Evropske-Unije-projekte-2	22	
12.04.2023	Portugal	https://nati00ns.eu/events/living-labs-missao-solo-horizonte-europa-portugal	198	
12.04.2023	Albania	https://nati00ns.eu/events/event-kombetar-mbi-angazhimin-e-shqiperise-ne-misionin-e-bashkimit-evropian-token	64	
17.04.2023	Germany	https://nati00ns.eu/events/national-engagement-event-eu-soil-mission-germany	20	Online only
20.04.2023	Cyprus	https://nati00ns.eu/events/national-engagement-event-eu-soil-mission-cyprus	31	
20.04.2023	Kosovo	https://nati00ns.eu/events/national-engagement-event-eu-soil-mission-pristina	79	
21.04.2023	Slovenia	https://nati00ns.eu/events/misiije-novost-programa-obzorje-evropa-slovenia	50	Online only
24.04.2023	Slovakia	https://nati00ns.eu/events/misia-poda-s-vami-pocita-slovensko	54	
25.04.2023	Luxembourg	https://nati00ns.eu/events/national-engagement-event-eu-soil-mission-luxembourg	30	Online only

Date	Country	Link	Participants	Notes
25.04.2023	Montenegro	https://nati00ns.eu/events/national-engagement-event-eu-soil-mission-montenegro	31	
26.04.2023	Greece	https://nati00ns.eu/events/nati00ns-national-engagement-event-greece	39	
28.04.2023	Lithuania	https://nati00ns.eu/events/lietuvos-dirvozemio-dabartis-ir-ateitis-bendradarbiavimo-sprendimai-sveiko-dirvozemio	31	
02.05.2023	Tunisia	https://nati00ns.eu/events/evenement-dengagement-national-du-projet-nati00ns-tunisia	45	
02.05.2023	Georgia	https://nati00ns.eu/events/national-engagement-event-eu-soil-mission-georgia	51	
04.05.2023	Malta	https://nati00ns.eu/events/national-engagement-event-malta	24	Online only
05.05.2023	Bosnia and Herzegovina	https://nati00ns.eu/events/nati00ns-dogadaj-nacionalnog-angazmana-u-misiji-eu-za-tlo-bosna-i-hercegovina	45	
09.05.2023	Czech Republic	https://nati00ns.eu/events/national-engagement-event-eu-soil-mission-czech-republic	46	
12.05.2023	Armenia	https://nati00ns.eu/events/national-engagement-event-eu-soil-mission-armenia	22	
15.05.2023	North Macedonia	https://nati00ns.eu/events/nati00ns-nastan-zanacionalen-angazhman-vo-severna-makedonija-zdrava-pochva-zeleni-biznisi	79	
16.05.2023	Poland	https://nati00ns.eu/events/ogolnopolskie-spotkanie-dotyczace-zaangazowania-w-misje-glebowa-ue-w-polsce	84	Online only
17.05.2023	Netherlands	https://nati00ns.eu/events/nationaal-engagement-evenement-over-de-eu-bodem-missie-nederland	50	
23.05.2023	Norway	https://nati00ns.eu/events/nati00ns-nasjonalt-engasjementsarrangement-om-eus-jordsmonns-misjon-i-norge	68	Online only
26.05.2023	Iceland	https://nati00ns.eu/events/islandi-iceland-event-1	27	Online only
29.05.2023	Estonia	https://nati00ns.eu/events/estonia-national-event-1	19	

Date	Country	Link	Participants	Notes
31.05.2023	Finland	https://natioons.eu/events/finland-national-event-1	28	Online only
02.06.2023	Croatia	https://natioons.eu/events/croatia-national-event-1	35	
05.06.2023	Latvia	https://natioons.eu/events/seminars-vai-mums-ir-veseliga-augsne-augsnes-problemas-un-inovativu-risinajumi-tas	16	
43 events		62.1 average participants		

Table 2. National Engagement Events - Data

2.3 National Co-organisers and Supporting Local Third-Party Entities

While NATIOONS partners were directly in charge of organising national events in their home countries, over the course of the first round each partner had also supported a national co-organiser in the planning, promotion and delivery of events in areas where NATIOONS was not directly represented by a partner.

The list of organisers and co-organisers can be found below.

Country/Region	NATIOONS liaison	National co-organiser
Albania	BIOSENSE	SCiDEV
Armenia	TRUST-IT	SIPAC
Austria	FUNDECYTPCTEX	Alpine Soil Partnership and the International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis
Belgium	ENOLL	Agrolink, VLAIO, Research Foundation Flanders, Flemish Department of Economy, Science & Innovation
Bosnia and Herzegovina	BIOSENSE	RTD Health Cluster, Banja Luka Regional Chamber of Commerce, Smart Village Knežica
Bulgaria	IRCEM	Institute Perspectives
Croatia	XIA	Croatian Society of Soil Science, Hrvatska zajednica inovatora
Cyprus	EIT FOOD	EIT FOOD Cyprus, CYENS
Czech Republic	IUNG	Technology Centre Prague
Denmark	AU	SEGES
Estonia	LAAS	METK
Finland	SLU	AgriHubi, Suomen Akatemia
France	FUNDECYT-PCTEX	INRAE and DEV'UP Centre-Val de Loire, MESR, RNSEST, ACTA
Georgia	TRUST-IT	Shota Rustaveli National Science Foundation of Georgia
Germany	FUNDECYT-PCTEX	University of Hohenheim
Greece	FUNDECYT-PCTEX	Q-PLAN and American Farm School

Country/Region	NATI00NS liaison	National co-organiser
Hungary	XIA	XIA
Iceland	SLU	Rannís, Háskólinn á Hólum, Háskólinn á Íslandi
Ireland	ENoLL	Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine (DAFM)
Israel	EIT FOOD	EIT Hub Israel, GrowingIL
Italy	TRUST-IT, POLIMI	
Kosovo	BIOSENSE	Innovation Centre Kosovo
Latvia	LAAS	LLKC
Lithuania	LAAS	Vytautas Magnus University Agriculture Academy
Luxembourg	ENoLL	Luxinnovation
Malta	BMED	Environmental & Resources Authority
Moldova	IRCEM	Academiei de Științe a Moldovei
Montenegro	BIOSENSE	Center of Excellence (FoodHub), University of Donja Gorica
Netherlands	FUNDECYT-PCTEX	RIVM (National Institute for Public Health and the Environment), Louis Bolk Institute, Wageningen, Aeres Hogeschool, Deltares
North Macedonia	BIOSENSE	ARNO, Agricultural Institute-Skopje
Norway	SLU	Landbruksdirektoratet, Norsk Landbruksrådgiving, Forskningsrådet, NIBIO, Ruralis
Poland	IUNG	Ministry of the Environment
Portugal	FUNDECYT-PCTEX	Portuguese National Innovation Agency and Centre Region Co-ordination and Development Commission
Romania	IRCEM	Ministry of Environment and Climate Change
Serbia	BIOSENSE	Mokrin House
Slovakia	IUNG	CVTI SR
Slovenia	XIA	Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Food
Spain	FUNDECYT-PCTEX & EIT FOOD	CDTI, CSIC-INIA
Sweden	SLU	Stockholm Environment Institute
Tunisia	BMED	ICARDA, Tunisia Horizon Europe, CGIAR
Turkey	EIT FOOD	Foodback
Ukraine	IRCEM	Izmail State University of Humanities
United Kingdom	FUNDECYT-PCTEX	UK KTN

Table 3. List of organisers and co-organisers

2.4 Centralised digital support to the implementation of the events

This section complements, extends and better clarify the description of the task 3.2, as it provides essential elements to understand how the national engagements events were implemented.

Trust-IT coordinated the organisation of the events with active support of the task partners (national co-organisers), as explained below, and the supporting local third-party entities.

Trust-IT has set up centralised digital support mechanism in order to harmonise the input coming from the national organisers and to ensure a consistent and effective implementation of the events, as outlined further below.

The organisation of more than 40 national engagement events in a short period of time implies bringing ideas or actions into agreement and to a consistent combination between what the national organisers and the supporting local third-party entities want to carry out and the NATIOONS visual identity and event format design. This harmonisation activity was necessary to ensure that the event complied with the NATIOONS standards in terms of presented content, visual identity, visibility.

This support mechanism was both centralised, because the information flow was managed by only one partner (Trust-IT) which had a complete overview of the process, and digital, since most of the supporting efforts was provided remotely through email exchanges, conference calls, creation and management of online forms, databases and video conference platforms.

Trust-IT was the main point of reference for the national organisers which were implementing in-person, hybrid and online events. This mechanism limited information loss and resource dispersion. Conversely, it optimised the capacity of the task partners to set up and manage a calendar of the events avoiding any potential clashes.

The following points briefly describe the phases of the centralised digital support mechanism, which were common to all the implemented national engagement events.

Phase	Description of the Process	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5	T6	T7
1	Draft of description of the National Engagement Event for the NATI00NS website, registration form, feedback survey in English	■						
2	Conference call or email exchange between Trust-IT and the National Organisers		■					
3	Agreement on the date and place of the event			■				
4	Localisation and customisation: Translation in local language and customisation of the drafts in phase 1 by the national organiser			■				
5	Creation of the graphics and visual content related to the specific event by Trust-IT			■				
6	Virtual meeting room set up on the video conference platform provided by Trust-IT			■				
7	Creation of the National Engagement Event webpage on the NATI00NS website, registration form, feedback survey in local language				■			
8	Event promotion through social media and other communication tools					■		
9	Registration Management					■		
10	Event implementation						■	
11	Feedback survey management							■

Table 4. Multi-Phase Timeline of the Centralised Digital Support Mechanism

1. Draft of description of the National Engagement Event for the NATIOONS website, registration form, feedback survey in English

Trust-IT prepares a draft of the National Engagement Event description in English. This description is used as a model for the descriptions of the specific national engagement events which are then uploaded to the NATIOONS website. Templates for the registration forms and feedback surveys are also created in this phase.

2. Conference call or email exchange between Trust-IT and the National Organisers

Trust-IT initiates a conference call or engages in an email exchange with the National Organisers. The purpose of this communication is to discuss and clarify the event requirements, objectives, and expectations.

3. Agreement on the date and place of the event

Trust-IT and the National Organisers collaborate to agree on the date and place of the event, if the latter is held in person. Factors such as availability, logistics, and relevance to the target audience are taken into account.

4. Localisation and Customisation

The draft materials, including the event description, are translated into the local language by the National Organiser, which customises the drafts to align them with local requirements and preferences.

5. Creation of the graphics and visual content related to the specific event by Trust-IT

Trust-IT creates graphics and visual content specific to the National Engagement Event. These visuals may include banners, posters, infographics, or other promotional materials.

6. Virtual meeting room set up on the video conference platform provided by Trust-IT

Trust-IT sets up a virtual meeting room on a video conference platform provided by Trust-IT. This room will serve as the online venue for the event, accommodating virtual participants.

7. Creation of the National Engagement Event webpage on the NATIOONS website, registration form, feedback survey in local language

Trust-IT creates a dedicated webpage on the NATIOONS website for the National Engagement Event. The webpage includes the event description, agenda, speakers' information, and relevant resources. A localised registration form and feedback survey are also included on the webpage in the local language.

8. Event promotion through social media and other communication tools

Trust-IT promotes the National Engagement Event through various communication channels, including social media. The national organisers and the supporting local third parties leverage their network and communication tools to reach the target audience and generate interest.

9. Registration Management

Trust-IT manages the registration process for the event, shares the related information with the national organisers and the supporting local third parties and communicates logistical details to participants.

10. Event Implementation

The National Engagement Event takes place as planned, either in-person, hybrid, or online. Trust-IT offers its support to the use of the tools, such as Zoom Meeting Platform, Sli.do and Mural, throughout the event, in case it is needed, to ensure smooth execution.

11. Feedback Survey Management

After the event, organisers distribute the feedback surveys to participants. Then Trust-IT collects responses, and analyses the feedback received to draft a bird’s eye analysis of the overall round of events, while national organisers examine data related to the single national event for specific evaluations.

Throughout the entire process, Trust-IT acts as the central point of contact, coordinating and harmonising the efforts of the National Organisers. The centralised digital support mechanism has enabled effective communication, information sharing, and resource management, resulting in a successful and impactful round of National Engagement Events.

3 Evaluation and Lessons Learned

Item	Target KPI	Status
National Engagement Events	43 engagement events per round 60 avg. participants (combined physical and remote)	43 events organised 62 average participants
Participants in national events	>40% female participants >10% participants not coming from agriculture land use	53% female participants 21% non-agriculture land use type as first choice
Feedback surveys	>50% positive responses to post-event surveys	>4 out of 5 average response on content, organisation and involvement

Table 5. Target KPIs for National Engagement Events

3.1 Evaluation Framework

The evaluation framework of the National Engagement events focuses on three key priorities:

Priority 1: Raising awareness and generating a shared sense of ownership

The first priority of the events is to raise awareness among attendees of the Soil Mission and specifically the topics on LLs in the Horizon Europe Work Programme 2023, and additionally, the value of soils and their significance in various sectors and scales. The objective is to highlight the importance of changing land management practices to enable soil restoration and contribute to sustainable production and consumption systems. The events aim to convey the Mission's policy initiatives and implementation plan, tailoring the messages with clear examples to convince stakeholders of the benefits of engaging in the Mission activities. The

events also showcase specific soil health challenges across regions, serving as a foundation for discussions and the formation of regional Living Labs.

Priority 2: Providing guidance on soil health LLs and LHs

The second priority is to instruct potential applicants on the concept and criteria for soil health Living Labs (LLs) and Lighthouses (LHs). The events provide detailed information on the process of setting up and running LLs and LHs, incorporating the formal explanations and criteria established by the Mission. Through the contribution of ENoLL, event organisers offer accurate information on LLs and LHs. Real-life examples of LLs for different land uses are shared, highlighting the life cycle of a LL site. Outputs from PREPSOIL and EJP SOIL are referenced, serving as inspiring examples of already running living labs in Serbia, Hungary, Poland and Italy, covering different types of land uses and good practices.

Priority 3: Orienting participants for post-event work

The third priority involves orienting participants towards post-event activities, such as fostering cross-regional and cross-national networking, and guiding participants towards capacity-building opportunities. Attendees are encouraged to continue discussions at the regional level to prepare schemes for regional LLs, utilising virtual spaces such as the Communities of Practice online forum provided by PREPSOIL. Participants are informed about the coaching sessions, matchmaking B2B meetings, capacity-building webinars, and other activities offered by NATIOONS.

The evaluation framework in D3.2 builds on the monitoring and internal evaluation framework as it is described in the overarching event plan (D3.1), which lists a set of indicators to measure event success, offering acceptable value ranges in each country; procedures for internal KPI review. The main KPI is the number of attendees. The objective was to target at least 60 combined online and physical attendees in each event on average. The project consortium has been able to meet and overcome that threshold. Additionally, an integral part of the evaluation framework has been the design and release of tailored registration forms and post-event surveys that allowed to measure: female presence among attendees (targeting >40%; reached value 53%), balanced representation of all type of land use stakeholders (targeting at least 10% for non-agriculture land uses; 21% of stakeholders ticked non-agriculture land use type as first choice), as well as successful awareness raised and clear view of the LL application process (targeting >50% attendees answering positively to post-event surveys; the average response on content, organisation and involvement was >4 out of 5).

Based on the lists of priorities and indicators, an evaluation methodology for the National Engagement events revolves around two pillars: Survey analysis and Assessment of the feedback of the national organisers.

1. The **survey analysis** implies the collation and systematisation of the responses from the feedback survey. A quantitative analysis is performed by summarising and categorising responses based on the provided options and a qualitative analysis is carried out by reviewing and extracting insights from open-ended responses. The types of data that is collated and analysed is clustered around the following 9 categories:

a. Participant Demographics:

- Analyse the distribution of participants across different organisation types to understand the representation and engagement levels of various stakeholders.
- Assess the types of land practices that participants are involved in to identify the diversity of perspectives and expertise.

b. Event Attendance and Format:

- Evaluate the number and proportion of participants attending the events in person and online to assess the reach and accessibility of the events.
- Analyse the reasons for attending the events to understand the motivations and expectations of participants.
- Assess participant satisfaction with the event format in terms of duration and content quality.

c. Awareness and Involvement in EU Soil Mission:

- Determine the level of awareness and involvement of participants in the EU Soil Mission.
- Identify participants' interests and desired roles within the mission.

d. Relevance of Soil Mission Objectives:

- Analyse participants' perceptions of the relevance of the EU Soil Mission objectives to their region/country.
- Identify the most frequently selected objectives that participants consider important.

e. Barriers for Living Lab Formation:

- Identify barriers or challenges expressed by participants in initiating the formation of Living Labs in their regions.

f. Event Satisfaction:

- Evaluate participant ratings of the event in terms of organization, content, and the involvement of participants.
- Assess participant satisfaction with the event format in relation to duration and content quality.

g. Event Outcomes and Improvement Areas:

- Identify the event's helpful aspects, such as increased understanding of the Soil Mission, identification of relevant soil challenges, and inspiration for engagement in establishing Living Labs.
- Gather suggestions for improvement and areas where participants believe the events can be enhanced.

h. Experiences and Good Practices:

- Collect information on participants' knowledge of experiences or good practices related to soil health and Living Labs.
- Document details or weblinks provided by participants for further review.

i. Additional Events and Contact Information:

- Assess participants' interest in attending additional events focused on specific thematic areas in the creation of Living Labs.
 - Gather email addresses from participants who wish to receive a response from the project consortium regarding their questions.
2. By analysing the survey responses and synthesising the findings, this evaluation methodology is complemented by the **assessment of the direct feedback of the national co-organisers**. This is an added value, as the national organisers gained a closer look and a more realistic perception of the event deployment. This input is critical to optimise the second round of events. For this reason, a dedicated sli.do session is carried out involving the national co-organisers, which are invited to share their views and recommendations.

This evaluation framework enables the consortium to enhance the analysis by combining quantitative and qualitative methods, and categorising responses, conducting thematic analysis of open-ended responses to capture nuanced insights and participants' perspectives. It also allows to analyse the feedback based on participant characteristics such as organization type, land practices, or level of involvement in the EU Soil Mission. This segmentation can provide valuable insights into the specific needs, interests, and challenges faced by different participant groups.

Furthermore, this evaluation framework generates actionable recommendations for improving future events. These recommendations are specific, practical, and aligned with the identified areas for improvement, enabling event organisers to implement changes based on the evaluation findings (See section 3.4).

Such a methodology sets the ground for a feedback loop where the evaluation findings are shared with event organizers, stakeholders, and participants. This allows for ongoing dialogue and collaboration, ensuring that the evaluation results inform decision-making and contribute to iterative improvements in event planning and implementation.

3.2 Event Performance Measurement

3.2.1 Registration and participation

Performance measurement is essential to evaluate the effectiveness and impact of the National Engagement Events. Through systematic evaluation, organisers can gather valuable insights on attendance rates, participant feedback, stakeholder engagement, and achievement of objectives. This analysis helps identify strengths, areas for improvement, and informs decisions for future events.

The first obvious indicators that were taken into account were the numbers of registrants and participants at each event. For this purpose, a shared working document was made available to the consortium on Share-Point, where to keep track of statistics through the first round. Also, each national organiser had access to the lists of registrants updated routinely, to know for example which land use type stakeholders needed more support in terms of promotion. The continuous monitoring of the event registrations allowed organisers to implement actions to boost the number of registrants, such as increasing the direct messages at local level, leverage existing local networks and increasing the activities on social media accounts.

Through the first round of events, we have met our target KPI of at least 60 participants on average, with **62.1** participants.

In order to meet the needs of the soil health community, recorded events were also made available via the NATI00NS YouTube channel and collected in a playlist³, allowing people to also watch or rewatch them after the event had taken place.

Figure 1 Registrants by country/region

3.2.2 Feedback surveys

Aside from discussions and engagement at the events themselves, a feedback survey was envisioned in D3.1 as an additional channel to collect input from participants in the event. These surveys were also translated in the national languages and distributed after the conclusion of the events, encouraging participants to provide evaluations on the first round and ideas for the second round.

As is often the case, most participants did not go on to complete the survey after the event. Out of more than 2400 registered participants across events, slightly less than 100 filled out the form. Still, these numbers allow us to do some analysis in terms of the perceived quality of the events and to extract relevant comments from their submissions.

³ <https://youtube.com/playlist?list=PL48jYWfH7LrAR7hx6m7VQgSsMDxHmrnun>

Generally speaking, the events were highly appreciated under all the three aspects of content (4.4 out of 5 on average), organisation (4.3) and involvement (4.1).

One lesson learned for the second round is to make the surveys shorter and easier to fill in to attract more participation.

Content, Organisation and Involvement

Figure 2 User evaluation of the national engagement events

Several common themes emerged from the survey responses. Firstly, there was a request for more information on existing soil health Living Labs (LLs), indicating a desire to understand their scope and implementation in greater detail. Similarly, participants expressed a need for guidance on establishing LLs, suggesting a desire to engage more actively in this area. Another recurring feedback was the desire for more time dedicated to discussion and questions during the events, emphasising the importance of fostering interactive sessions. Additionally, participants requested a bit more information on Lighthouses, potentially indicating a desire to better comprehend their role and relevance within the context of the Mission. Lastly, participants highlighted the importance of receiving more practical details, indicating a need for clearer and more actionable information. These insightful comments provide valuable guidance for improving future National Engagement Events, ensuring they better meet the participants' needs and expectations. Many of the comments emerging from the national events were addressed also via the range of NATI00NS activities implemented through the spring and summer, such as the launch of the Matchmaking platform⁴, the Helpdesk

⁴ <https://nati00ns-soil-living-lab-matching.b2match.io/>

section⁵, the publication of the thematic factsheets⁶, and the organisation of extremely successful webinars⁷ on Living Labs and the Open Calls.

3.2.3 Evaluation from event organisers and co-organisers

Direct feedback from event organisers and co-organisers is especially precious, as they are the boots on the ground with the best feeling of events. Their input is extremely relevant towards the improvement of the second round of events.

For this reason, a dedicated sli.do session was carried out during the NATIOONS consortium meeting on 7 July 2023, also involving national co-organisers who shared their experiences during the discussion.

26 people took part in the interactive session, identifying their highlights and challenges from the events, as well as proposing suggestions for improvements in Year 2.

Which were the highlights of the events for you?

The top five choices in this question were the following:

- Networking (21 votes)
- Communication with NATIOONS team (15 votes)
- Materials (10 votes)
- Promotion (10 votes)
- Matchmaking (6 votes)

Getting in touch with other organisations and initiatives was seen as the key element of the engagement events, and the collaboration with the core NATIOONS team was positive for co-organisers outside of the consortium. In addition, materials provided by the NATIOONS (e.g., presentations, brochures...) and the promotion support (social media, visuals, newsletters...) were both useful.

Which were the most challenging aspects for you?

The top five choices in this question were the following:

- Inviting participants and promoting the event (23 votes)
- Following up after the event (11 votes)
- Carrying out the engagement session (10 votes)
- Technical management of the session at the venue (7 votes)
- Preparing the agenda (5 votes)

Most of the difficulties were linked to the very tight schedule that needed all events to take place in a specific time window, with the projects starting officially only in November 2022 and the consortium meeting in

⁵ <https://natio0ns.eu/helpdesk>

⁶ <https://natio0ns.eu/factsheets>

⁷ <https://natio0ns.eu/living-labs-webinars>

person the first time only in January 2023. Promotion was also affected by this, with some events organised in only two or three weeks to take advantage of useful windows at the national level or of the availability of specific venues. The matchmaking platform was not available right at the start of the events, so this had an impact on some of the earlier events in terms of following up.

How can we support in the second round of events?

The comments received in response to this question provided valuable insights and suggestions for enhancing the overall experience. Firstly, participants highlighted the importance of adopting a multidisciplinary approach, involving various stakeholders ranging from academia, nonprofits, social enterprises, citizen activists, and artists to create a comprehensive and diverse dialogue on the topic. Furthermore, there was a call for greater involvement of national institutions in raising awareness about soil restoration and protection. Participants also expressed the need for more practical examples and guidance on Living Labs, including directions from the Soil Mission on relevant themes to be included in proposals. Effective communication and engagement were highlighted through suggestions for better partner-to-partner communication and the utilisation of social media platforms for promotional support. The desire for continuous engagement, feedback, and involvement of the Soil Mission was evident, as well as the need to ensure representation from various soil types and land uses. Participants also emphasised the importance of automation and streamlining processes to avoid bottlenecks. These insightful comments provide a clear roadmap for supporting the second round of events, ensuring a more inclusive, informative, and impactful experience.

3.3 Analysis of Registrants in Phase 1

Some of our target KPIs were linked to demographics and the background of the people involved in NATIOONS activities. At the end of the first round of events, we have collected information about all registrants in order to analyse some key elements.

As mentioned in 3.2.2, more than 2400 people registered for our events across EU Member States and Associated Countries, providing relevant information about the soil health community. Since not all questions were mandatory, numbers vary slightly between the different items, but at least 2000 respondents are counted for each chart.

Gender (registrants)

Figure 3 Gender representation at events

Since division in land use types is often not clear-cut, we enabled registrants to indicate a multiple choice for the land use type of their organisations, focusing on four main categories (agriculture, urban, forestry/nature, (post)industrial). Agriculture was the most chosen, by 1762 registrants, followed by forestry and/or nature at 821, urban at 566 and (post)industrial with 377, as shown in Figure 4. To count more easily the types of use, we have aggregated in Figure 5 all responses by their first choice, and there we can see that agriculture accounted for 79.1% of responses, while the other three types for 20.9%, about twice the target KPI of 10% that we had envisioned in D3.1.

Figure 4 Land use type (multiple choice)

First choice of land use type (registrants)

Figure 5 First choice of land use type

3.4 Planning Improvements for Round #2: Measures to Ensuring a Balanced Coverage of the Different Types of Stakeholders in Phase 2

Based on the information, data and considerations collated and mentioned in section 3. Evaluation and Lessons Learned, the consortium members agreed to pursue the following set of improvements for the Second Round of Events (Round #2):

1. **Shorter and More Accessible Feedback Surveys:** Based on the feedback from the first round, it is recommended to make the surveys shorter and easier to fill out in order to encourage higher participation rates. This can be achieved by streamlining the survey questions and ensuring clarity in the instructions. By doing so, organisers can gather more comprehensive feedback from participants to identify areas of improvement and address their specific needs.
2. **Enhanced Practical Information on Soil Health Living Labs (LLs):** Responding to the feedback from participants, it is important to provide more detailed information on existing LLs, their scope, and implementation. This can include showcasing successful LL examples, highlighting their impact, and sharing best practices. Additionally, guidance on establishing LLs should be provided to empower participants to actively engage in this area. Participants highlighted

the importance of receiving practical details and actionable information. In response, organisers should focus on delivering clear, concise, and practical information that participants can easily implement in their respective contexts. This can include providing step-by-step guides, case studies, and resources that support participants in their soil health initiatives.

3. **Increased Interaction and Discussion Opportunities:** Participants expressed a desire for more time dedicated to discussions and questions during the events. To address this, organisers should allocate sufficient time within the event agenda for interactive sessions, panel discussions, and Q&A sessions. This will foster meaningful engagement, knowledge sharing, and networking among participants.
4. **Inclusion and Representation:** Ensure a balanced coverage of different types of stakeholders and soil types in the events. Make deliberate efforts to attract and involve participants from various sectors and land use interests, especially the urban, forestry/nature, and (post)industrial sectors. This can be achieved by targeted outreach, personalised invitations, and communication campaigns towards relevant networks and organisations representing these sectors. It is then recommended to adopt a multidisciplinary approach in the event implementation to foster a comprehensive dialogue. This means to involve stakeholders, other than academia and farmer organisations, such as nonprofits, social enterprises, citizen activists, and artists, to bring diverse perspectives and expertise to the discussions. Collaboration with Sector-Specific Networks with different background can leverage their expertise and reach. Engage these networks as event co-host, panel chairs or speakers to ensure their active involvement in promoting the events within their communities. This collaboration can help ensure a balanced coverage of different stakeholder types and facilitate targeted engagement. Designing event sessions and topics that cater to the specific interests and needs of different stakeholder groups can also be achieved by offering parallel sessions or tracks focusing on sector-specific challenges, opportunities, and best practices. Tailor the content and format to address the specific requirements and priorities of each stakeholder group. Efforts should be made to actively engage national institutions and organisations to raise awareness about soil restoration and protection.
5. **Continuous Engagement and Feedback:** Maintain continuous engagement with participants and stakeholders between events through the already well-established channels for ongoing communication, such as dedicated newsletters and the matchmaking platform. Actively seek and incorporate participant feedback to ensure that their voices are heard, and their suggestions are considered for future improvements.

By implementing these improvements and measures, the second round of events will be more inclusive, informative, and impactful. It will foster engagement among diverse stakeholders, provide practical guidance, and promote collaboration in achieving the objectives of the EU Soil Mission.

4 Capitalising on Evaluation Takeaways

4.1 Integration with Capacity Building Activities (T4.3)

The capacity building activities organised by Task 4.3 took place after the end of the first round of events, building on the requirements acquired via the questions and comments collected through the 43 events, the matchmaking platform, as well as via the helpdesk.

Three webinars were held between 22 June and 6 July⁸, to raise awareness of the specific concept of regional soil health Living Labs, the funding available under the Mission 'A Soil Deal for Europe' Living Lab topics as well as the application process.

In particular, the series was promoted to all the 2000+ registrants who had expressed interest in learning more and receiving the NATIOONS newsletter, building a solid community interested in soil health and the open calls. Furthermore, the NCPs, the Mission Board, the Key Network Group and the coordinators and dissemination managers of the projects funded by the Soil Mission received an invitation to help share the events before the first webinar.

The success of Task 3.2 contributed to the following success of Task 4.3 by putting in place practices for registrations, promotion and execution of events.

- 22 June 2023 - The Living Lab essentials – how to set up a Living Lab (430 participants)
- 29 June 2023 - Business and governance models for LL life cycle (192 participants)
- 6 July 2023 - Core elements and specificities of the Living Lab topics (167 participants)

The national events also provided a promotional stage for the matchmaking platform managed in T4.4⁹, supporting the growth in terms of users across countries and regions (more than 470 registrants as of July 2023).

As a testament to the tight interconnection of all tasks in NATIOONS, both the national events and webinars are in turn influencing the content and delivery of the upcoming online thematic events organised in T3.3 in Year 2.

4.2 Recommendations for Mission Secretariat, Mission Implementation Platform and SOILL (Identifying Countries/Regions with Support Needs)

The intelligence gathered from the national engagement events can significantly contribute to provide a set of recommendations for the Mission Secretariat, the Mission Implementation Platform and SOILL (the Soil Health Living Lab network support structure resulting from the Framework Partnership Agreement). This section identifies the domains of intervention of the recommendations that will be more extensively described in D3.3, after the second round of events.

⁸ <https://nati00ns.eu/living-labs-webinars>

⁹ <https://nati00ns-soil-living-lab-matching.b2match.io/>

The information collected from the events, including feedback, participant interests, and requests for more information on LLs, can help identify potential LLs across different regions. By analysing the data, organizers can identify areas with high interest and engagement in soil health initiatives, allowing them to target those regions for establishing LLs.

The events provided an opportunity to discuss and identify specific and less-debated soil health challenges in different regions and land use types. This information is shared with PREPSOIL to support their work on mapping the soil health challenges across Europe. By understanding the specific challenges in each region, the Mission Secretariat, SOILL and other Soil Mission funded projects can provide targeted resources, expertise, and solutions to address those challenges effectively.

The feedback and requests for guidance on LL establishment indicate a strong interest among participants in actively engaging in LL initiatives. Based on the evidence NATIOONS collates through the national engagement event implementation, SOILL can develop comprehensive guidelines, toolkits, and resources to assist interested parties in establishing LLs. This guidance can cover various aspects, including governance models, stakeholder engagement strategies, funding opportunities, and monitoring and evaluation frameworks.

Additionally, the intelligence gathered from the events can inform the development of stakeholder engagement strategies within the SOILL project. By understanding the diverse range of the stakeholders' needs involved in soil health initiatives, the support structure can tailor its engagement approaches to effectively involve actors and themes that need further stimulation, across the geographical, sectoral, land use dimensions. This will foster a collaborative and inclusive environment for knowledge exchange and co-creation within the LL network.

Lastly, the feedback and identified challenges will feed the development of the capacity building and training programs within SOILL. By addressing the identified barriers, such as lack of knowledge on LL concepts, or financial constraints, SOILL can design capacity building initiatives to equip LL actors with the necessary skills, knowledge, and resources to effectively operate and contribute to the LL network.

4.3 Spotlight on national events

NATIOONS embarked on a journey to raise awareness of the EU Soil Mission and its open calls through 43 national events held across European Union member states and associated countries. The insights gathered during these events have been instrumental in view of better shaping the forthcoming round of events in 2024. This section sheds light on the experiences coming from five representative national events held in Israel, Turkey, Cyprus, Portugal, and Germany, which showcase both successes and lessons learned.

Israel

Location: Tel Aviv

Israel's event, strategically located in Tel Aviv, drew significant physical attendance, enabling us to meet our attendance-related KPI. A pivotal partnership between EIT Food, EIT Hub Israel, and GrowingIL added value to the event by harnessing the stakeholder networks of the three entities. 141 attendees seized the opportunity to network and explore potential collaborations for the creation of Living Labs and consortia.

Turkey

Location: Istanbul

Turkey's event took place in Istanbul, with over 40 physical attendees and approximately 30 online participants. The event provided a platform for attendees to gain a deeper understanding of the Soil Mission call while the time reserved for networking was appreciated as it fostered potential opportunities for fruitful collaborations.

Cyprus

Location: Nicosia

Cyprus, despite its smaller stakeholder base, hosted a dynamic and interactive onsite event, attracting around 20 physical attendees. Engaging discussions during the event led to the emergence of productive collaborations. Insights in the post-event analysis suggest that scheduling the next event in early March 2024 or between late September and November 2023 could enhance stakeholder engagement and boost attendance in Cyprus.

Portugal

Location: Lisbon

Portugal's event generated considerable anticipation as it was the first national event on the Soil Mission and Living Labs in the country. The event's theme sparked curiosity, reflected in the impressive attendance (198 participants). The national co-organisers, which are experienced facilitators of Portuguese EU funding programs, provided a trusted source of information that resonated with potential applicants. Thoughtful and balanced event programming also encouraged physical attendance.

Germany

Virtual Event

Germany's unique circumstances dictated a virtual event due to a previous large national event organised by the National Contact Point (NCP) in 2022. The NCP was well-prepared for the Living Labs theme. The decision to host a virtual event was influenced by limited time for preparation and the

country's tightly scheduled agendas. Unfortunately, NATIOONS only managed to attract 17 participants to the event. This experience proved to be a valuable lesson for planning the 2024 NATIOONS round of events, where the event can be organised well in advance.

These five case studies of Israel, Turkey, Cyprus, Portugal, and Germany illustrate the diverse experiences encountered during these events, with each offering helpful indications for future planning.

5 Conclusion

With events held in 43 EU Member States and Associated Countries, the primary goal of raising awareness about the EU Soil Mission and its open calls was effectively achieved. The valuable feedback collected from these events is playing a pivotal role in shaping the upcoming round of events scheduled for 2024.

In addition to the success of the national engagement events in terms of participant turnout and feedback collection, it is important to highlight the broader positive impact these outcomes have had on other tasks within the NATIOONS project. The valuable insights gathered from the engagement events have not only informed the planning and execution of subsequent rounds of events in 2024 but have also played a crucial role in enhancing various project components.

The engagement events have paved the way for the development of highly effective webinars, which have further expanded the reach and impact of the EU Soil Mission. Leveraging the knowledge and expertise gained from the engagement events, these webinars have provided a platform for in-depth discussions and knowledge exchange among experts, stakeholders, and interested individuals. By capitalising on the momentum generated by the national engagement events, the webinars have fostered a deeper understanding of the EU Soil Mission and open calls, fostering a more engaged and informed community.

Furthermore, the information collected from the engagement events has proven relevant in the growth of the NATIOONS matchmaking platform. This platform serves as a dynamic hub, connecting researchers, innovators, and potential partners with common interests and goals in the field of soil preservation and revitalization. By incorporating the specific needs and preferences expressed by participants during the national engagement events, the matchmaking platform has been tailored to ensure optimal networking and collaboration opportunities, thus catalysing the generation of innovative solutions and impactful projects.

Building upon the success of the engagement events, the forthcoming online thematic events will benefit from the lessons learned and participant insights gathered during round one. The valuable feedback collected has contributed to the identification of key topics and areas of interest within

the EU Soil Mission, ensuring that the upcoming thematic events address the most pressing challenges and opportunities in a targeted and impactful manner. By leveraging the outcomes of the engagement events, these thematic events will provide a forum for deep dives into specific soil-related issues, promoting knowledge sharing, cross-pollination of ideas, and the formation of new collaborations.

In conclusion, the national engagement events have reverberated across various tasks within the project, including strengthening of collaboration efforts between partners and with the national co-organisers. The ongoing collaboration and engagement of stakeholders and participants will continue to drive the NATIOONS journey, ultimately leading to significant advancements in the preservation and revitalisation of soil health throughout Europe.

Annex 1 – Statistics from national events

A breakdown with key statistics from the national events can be found in the table below. Please note again that not all registrants have filled out all the optional questions, and that not all events have used the same questions (e.g., those organised within third-party initiatives).

Percentage of female registrants

National Event	Female	Male	Non-binary	Prefer not to say	Total	% women
Albania	27	15			42	64,3%
Armenia	18	7			25	72,00%
Belgium	25	21	1		47	53,2%
Bosnia & Herzegovina	17	18			35	48,6%
Bulgaria	48	27	1		76	63,2%
Croatia	13	10			23	56,5%
Cyprus	9	12		1	22	40,9%
Czechia	20	17			37	54,05%
Denmark	21	37			58	36,2%
Estonia	9	3			12	75,00%
Finland	12	8			20	60,00%
Georgia	17	22			39	43,6%
Germany	9	8			17	53%
Greece	31	23			54	57,5%
Hungary	35	50			85	41,2%
Iceland	10	10			20	50,00%
Ireland	13	13		2	28	46,4%
Israel	43	67			110	39,1%
Italy	59	45			104	56,7%
Kosovo	15	18			33	45,4%
Luxembourg	14	18		1	33	42,4%
Malta	6	10			16	37,5%
Moldova	31	35			66	47%
Montenegro	21	7			28	75,00%
Netherlands	19	20		1	40	47,50%
North Macedonia	57	42			99	57,60%
Norway	38	35			73	52,05%
Poland	62	36			98	63,30%
Portugal	115	65	1	2	183	62,90%
Romania	48	61		2	111	43,2%
Serbia	32	45			77	41,6%
Slovakia	21	20			41	51,2%
Spain	84	56	1	2	143	58,7%
Sweden	19	11			30	63,3%
Tunisia	21	25			46	45,6%
Turkey	55	33	1	6	95	57,9%
Ukraine	10	7			17	58,8%

Land use type of registrants

National Event	(Post) Industrial	Agriculture	Forestry and/or Nature	Urban	% non-agriculture
Albania	3	10	4	13	66,7%
Armenia	1	20	2	1	16,7%
Belgium	1	37	6		15,9%
Bosnia & Herzegovina		31	2	2	11,4%
Bulgaria	3	69	5	12	22,5%
Croatia	0	21	1	0	4,5%
Cyprus	1	15	3	3	31,8%
Czechia	2	37	2	1	11,9%
Denmark	0	1	0	0	0,0%
Estonia	0	15	0	0	0,0%
Finland	0	15	7	2	37,5%
Georgia	5	8	16	0	72,4%
Germany	1	13	0	0	7,1%
Greece	2	49	0	1	5,8%
Hungary	2	78	6	2	11,4%
Iceland	1	18	6	2	33,3%
Ireland		23	4		14,8%
Israel	4	109	1	10	12,1%
Italy	5	90	5	14	21,1%
Kosovo	4	24	4	2	29,4%
Luxembourg	2	29	3	2	19,4%
Malta	0	11	3	3	35,3%
Moldova	0	58	7	3	14,7%
Montenegro	1	20	2	1	16,7%
Netherlands	4	39	1	9	26,4%
North Macedonia	3	60	11	9	27,7%

National Event	(Post) Industrial	Agriculture	Forestry and/or Nature	Urban	% non-agriculture
Norway	0	74	3	1	5,1%
Poland	2	97	3	1	5,8%
Portugal	4	123	6	64	37,6%
Romania	12	82	10	14	30,5%
Serbia	2	64	3	0	7,2%
Slovakia	1	43	2	0	6,5%
Spain	12	104	1	34	31,1%
Sweden	1	28	7	1	24,3%
Tunisia	2	44	0	0	4,3%
Turkey	2	93	4	8	13,1%
Ukraine	0	15	0	2	11,8%

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